

Cyclic voltammetric studies of oxovanadium(IV) complexes derived from 2,2'-bipyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline in nonaqueous media

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Abstract : The electrochemical behaviour of oxovanadium(IV) complexes, $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ (where, bipy = 2,2'-bipyridine and phen = 1,10-phenanthroline) have been examined in DMSO and DMF with 0.1 M TBAP using cyclic voltammetry at a Pt working electrode. It is found that $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ complexes are irreversibly oxidized ($\text{VO}^{2+/3+}$) with anodic peak potential, $E_{\text{pa}_1} \approx 1.10$ V vs SCE at 200 mV s^{-1} . The initial reduction of these complexes in DMSO and DMF media revealed two irreversible cathodic peaks with $E_{\text{pc}_1} = -0.96$ to -1.13 V and $E_{\text{pc}_2} = -1.17$ to -1.30 V vs SCE. It should be mentioned that dependence of I_{pa_1} or I_{pc_1} on $v^{1/2}$ is linear without any intercept. This suggests that the redox processes a_1 and c_1 are diffusion controlled. It is also observed that the oxidation of bipy complex is easier while reduction is difficult in comparison to phen complex in a given medium.

Keywords : Cyclic voltammetry, electrochemistry, imines, VO^{2+} complexes.

Introduction

The coordination chemistry of oxovanadium(IV) complexes has growing applications in catalysis¹, therapeutics² and biological activity³. Vanadium containing compounds have their utility as insulin mimetic⁴ and antiameobic agent^{5a}. Vanadium dependent enzymes, mainly nitrogenases and haloperoxidases are still a subject for intensive biochemical investigation^{5b}.

In continuation to our earlier work^{6(a,b)} on electrochemical and EPR spectral studies on oxovanadium(IV) complexes with tridentate and tetradentate Schiff base ligands and recent findings about the better anticancer activity^{7(a,b)} of bis-chelated phenanthroline containing oxovanadium(IV) complexes than the mono-chelated phenanthroline complexes in human cells and also the spermicidal activity^{7c} of oxovanadium(IV) complexes of bipy, phen and derivatives in humans has motivated us to investigate the electrochemical behavior of such bio-active complexes because electrochemistry is comparable to the redox reactions occurring in biological systems as both involve heterogeneous charge transfer. We report herein the cyclic voltammetric behavior of square pyramidal oxovanadium(IV) complexes, $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ involving 4N,O donor set in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and dimethylformamide (DMF). The struc-

tures of the ligands and the square pyramidal complexes are shown below :

Results and discussion

It should be mentioned that the electrochemical behaviour of square pyramidal $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ complexes is almost similar under similar experimental conditions and their voltammograms exhibit quite similar pattern. The cyclic voltammetric data are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

A cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ complex in DMSO/0.1 M TBAP at a Pt working electrode at 200 mV s^{-1} is shown in Fig. 1(a,b). A positive scan (Fig. 1(b)) initiated at 0.0 V in the potential range from +1.25 to -1.50 V vs SCE reveals an irreversible oxidation peak (a_1) at +1.05 V in the forward scan and three partly overlapped irreversible cathodic waves (marked as c_1' , c_1 and c_2) are observed at -0.93 , -1.13 and -1.27 V, respectively in the reverse cycle (Table 1) (Fig. 1(a)). It is noteworthy that a potential scan initiated in the negative direction at 0.0 V shows only two irreversible ca-

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ complex in DMSO/0.1 M TBAP at 200 mV s^{-1} ; negative scan (a); positive scan (b).

thodic peaks c_1 and c_2 in the forward cycle and two irreversible small anodic peaks a_1 and a''_1 at -0.50 and $+0.62 \text{ V}$, respectively, in addition to large anodic peak a_1 in the reverse scan. It is evident from the voltammograms (Fig. 1(a and b)) that the cathodic peak c'_1 is dependent on the anodic peak a_1 and the anodic peak a''_1 is dependent on the cathodic process c'_1 . It must be noted that solutions containing 2 mM VOSO_4 or 1 mM bipy or phen in DMSO or DMF containing 0.1 M TBAP do not show any electrochemistry (no redox process) in the potential range studied, clearly indicating that the observed redox peaks in these complexes are metal-based only. Also a plot of I_{pa_1} or I_{pc_1} vs square root of the scan rate ($v^{1/2}$) gives a straight line passing through origin, suggesting that the redox processes (a_1 and c_1) are diffusion-controlled^{8,9} for both the complexes in the given media. Coulometry of these complexes (1 mM) performed at constant potential ($+1.20 \text{ V vs SCE}$) in DMSO/DMF containing 0.1 M TBAP has shown that a single electron is involved per molecule of the complex ($\text{VO}^{2+/3+}$). On the basis of these results, the anodic process (a_1) may be attributed to the diffusion-controlled irreversible single-electron oxidation of the complex, $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ to $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{3+}$, which is unstable under the experimental conditions and that the redox process involves ECE mechanism^{6a,8,9}.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ complex in DMF/0.1 M TBAP at 100 mV s^{-1} ; negative scan (a); positive scan (b).

Thus, the redox process (c'_1) may be assigned to irreversible reduction of the complex species (P) into some lower oxidation state. On the otherhand, cathodic processes c_1 and c_2 are due to the reduction of $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ into lower valent non-oxovanadium(III) complex species. It is noteworthy that mononuclear V^{III} complexes form six-coordinate non-oxo complexes¹⁰. It is obvious that VO^{2+} complexes on reduction would yield V^{III} or lower valent species because both the reduction processes c_1 and c_2 involve metal-based electron-transfer reactions¹¹.

Fig. 2(a,b) show the cyclic voltammograms of $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ complex in DMF/0.1 M TBAP at 100 mV s^{-1} in the potential range from $+1.375$ to -1.50 V vs SCE . A positive scan (Fig. 2(b)) initiated at -0.15 V shows an irreversible anodic peak (a_1) at $+1.10 \text{ V}$ in the forward cycle and three irreversible cathodic peaks c'_1 , c_1 and c_2 located at $+0.18$, -1.05 and -1.25 V , respec-

Table 1. CV data for $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ complex in DMSO and DMF containing 0.1 M TBAP

Scan rate (mV s^{-1})	E_{pa_1} (V)	E_{pc_1}' (V)	I_{pa_1} (μA)	I_{pc_1}' (μA)	E_{pc_1} (V)	$E_{pc_2}^a$ (V)	I_{pc_1} (μA)	E_{pa_1}' (V)	E_{pa_1}'' (V)
In DMSO									
25	+0.95	NA	3.0	–	–1.10	–1.22	2.25	NA	NA
50	+0.97	–0.90	4.2	1.00	–1.12	–1.25	3.00	NA	NA
100	+1.00	–0.92	6.0	1.25	–1.13	–1.27	4.50	–0.50	+0.60
200	+1.05	–0.93	8.2	1.75	–1.14	–1.30	6.00	–0.50	+0.62
300	+1.07	–0.95	10.0	2.25	–1.15	–1.31	7.50	–0.50	+0.63
400	+1.08	–0.97	11.5	2.75	–1.17	–1.32	8.75	–0.50	+0.63
500	+1.09	–0.98	13.0	3.00	–1.18	–1.33	9.50	–0.50	+0.65
In DMF									
25	+0.98	NA	3.75	–	–1.04	–1.20	2.50	–0.65	NA
50	+1.02	+0.22	5.00	0.75	–1.05	–1.22	3.50	–0.63	NA
100	+1.07	+0.20	7.25	1.00	–1.05	–1.24	5.00	–0.58	NA
200	+1.10	+0.18	10.00	1.25	–1.06	–1.25	6.75	–0.54	NA
300	+1.15	+0.16	12.00	2.00	–1.07	–1.26	8.00	–0.52	NA
400	+1.17	+0.14	14.25	2.50	–1.08	–1.27	9.75	–0.50	NA
500	+1.20	+0.12	16.00	3.00	–1.09	–1.28	10.75	–0.46	NA

^a I_{pc_2} and I_{pa_1}' is not measurable; NA, not appeared.

tively in the reverse cycle. Further, reversal of the scan direction at -1.50 V exhibits one irreversible anodic peak, a_1' at -0.54 V (Fig. 2(b), Table 1). It should be noted that the small cathodic peak c_1' is dependent on intense anodic peak (a_1 at $+1.1$ V) while the small anodic peak (a_1' at -0.54 V) is dependent on large cathodic peak (c_1 at -1.05 V). These facts suggest that the processes of electro-oxidation and electro-reduction of $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ complex in DMF/0.1 M TBAP are ECE type^{8,9} due to the fact that the corresponding cathodic peak (of a_1) and anodic peaks (of c_1 and c_2) are not observed in the scan rate range studied (Fig. 2(a)).

A perusal of the electrochemical data reveals that in a given solvent the cathodic peak potentials (E_{pc_1} and E_{pc_2}) are more negative for $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ complex than for $[\text{VO}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ (Tables 1 and 2). This indicates that the reduction of $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ complex is more difficult than that of $[\text{VO}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ complex, suggesting that there is more electron density on the metal centre in $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ complex. This is in line with the better σ -donor ability of bipy ligand¹² compared to phen. As expected, the oxidation of bipy complex is also easier compared to the phen complex. It is found that the peak potentials (E_{pa_1} , E_{pc_1} and E_{pc_2}) in DMF are more positive compared to those in DMSO for both the $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ and the $[\text{VO}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ complexes. This is in accordance with the better donor ability¹³ (donor number) of DMSO as compared to DMF

(Tables 1 and 2).

Experimental

The details of the electrochemical measurements are already described in our earlier papers^{7a,8}. Pt was used as a working electrode. The saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used as reference electrode ($E^0 = +242$ mV vs NHE). All experiments were performed at 25 ± 1 °C in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and dimethylformamide (DMF) containing 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP). Analytical grade chemicals were used without any further purification. TBAP (Fluka), $\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2,2'-bipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline, DMF and DMSO (E. Merck) were procured from different commercial sources and were used as such without further purification. The coulometric measurements were made using BAS Electrochemical System Model EPSILON using Carbon Vitrious Electrode as working electrode, Ag/AgCl as a reference and coiled Pt wire as auxillary electrode. The concentration of the freshly prepared solutions of the complexes was 2×10^{-3} M in the given solvent.

Preparation of complexes :

The oxovanadium(IV) complexes, $[\text{VO}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ were synthesized based on the previously published procedure¹⁴. The purity of the complexes was checked by elemental analyses.

Table 2. Cyclic voltammetric data for $[\text{VO}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ complex in DMSO and DMF containing 0.1 M TBAP

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pa_1} (V)	E_{pc_1}' (V)	I_{pa_1} (μA)	I_{pc_1}' (μA)	E_{pc_1} (V)	$E_{pc_2}^a$ (V)	I_{pc_1} (μA)	E_{pa_1}' (V)	E_{pa_1}'' (V)
In DMSO									
25	+1.00	NA	2.50	-	-0.94	-1.16	2.00	NA	NA
50	+1.02	-0.86	3.75	0.75	-0.96	-1.19	2.75	NA	NA
100	+1.05	-0.88	5.50	1.00	-0.99	-1.21	4.00	-0.53	+0.57
200	+1.09	-0.90	7.50	1.50	-1.02	-1.22	5.25	-0.53	+0.58
300	+1.11	-0.92	9.00	2.00	-1.05	-1.24	6.50	-0.52	+0.59
400	+1.13	-0.93	10.75	2.50	-1.07	-1.26	7.75	-0.52	+0.61
500	+1.15	-0.95	12.00	2.75	-1.08	-1.29	8.50	-0.52	+0.63
In DMF									
25	+1.04	NA	3.00	-	-0.90	-1.10	2.25	-0.61	NA
50	+1.06	+0.12	4.75	NM	-0.92	-1.12	3.05	-0.58	NA
100	+1.08	+0.10	6.50	0.75	-0.94	-1.15	4.25	-0.55	NA
200	+1.12	+0.09	9.25	1.00	-0.96	-1.17	6.00	-0.52	NA
300	+1.14	+0.07	11.25	1.25	-0.98	-1.19	7.50	-0.49	NA
400	+1.16	+0.05	13.00	2.00	-1.01	-1.21	8.75	-0.46	NA
500	+1.19	+0.03	14.50	2.50	-1.03	-1.23	9.50	-0.43	NA

^a I_{pc_2} not measurable.**References**

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